

Synthesis and Characterisation of Dichlorodi(4-t-butylphenoxo)titanium(IV)

K. C. MALHOTRA, NEERAJ SHARMA, S. S. BHATT and S. C. CHAUDHRY*

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Summer Hill, Shimla-171 005

Manuscript received 21 December 1992, revised 17 June 1993, accepted 23 June 1993

The use of sterically demanding ligands is currently receiving considerable attention¹. In particular, Chamberlain and Rothwell² reported studies involving the large 2,6-di-t-butylphenoxide ligand. Interesting observations include intramolecular C-H activation via metallation of t-butyl group of the phenoxide. In continuation of our recent work on the isolation and characterisation of titanium tetra-t-butylphenoxide³, we now report the synthesis of dichlorodi (4-t-butylphenoxo) titanium(IV), $\text{TiCl}_2\text{-(OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4)}_2$ (**1**) using TiCl_4 and 4-t-butylphenol. Addition compounds of **1** with some aliphatic amines such as diethylamine, n-propylamine, isopropylamine, n-butylamine and t-butylamine have also been prepared to establish their Lewis acid character.

Results and Discussion

Compound **1** is formed directly from TiCl_4 and 4-t-butylphenol in dry benzene under reflux. The elemental analysis agrees well with the expected stoichiometry. The compound is moisture-sensitive, dark red coloured solid, soluble in common organic solvents and has sharp melting point. Low molar conductance value ($1.63 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of millimolar solution in nitrobenzene, suggests its non-ionic nature. The cryoscopic molecular weight determination in nitrobenzene suggests that **1** is a monomer in contrast to chlorophenoxides of titanium(IV) reported as dimers⁴.

The ^1H nmr spectrum of **1** contained no

phenolic proton resonance. Further, the signal at δ 1.30 is assigned to t-butyl protons compared to δ 1.28 in pure phenol. Two signals for ring protons at δ 6.75 and 7.23 in pure phenol attributed to *ortho*- and *meta*-protons also experience down-field shift and are observed at δ 6.83 and 7.33. This overall downfield shift may be associated with the delocalisation of electrons from aromatic nucleus to the titanium atom⁵.

The broad ir band at $3400\text{--}3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (OH) in case of pure 4-t-butylphenol is missing in the complexes, suggesting the deprotonation of this group during compound formation which is also supported by nmr studies. Also the band at 1225 cm^{-1} (C-O) in 4-t-butylphenol is significantly lowered by 60 cm^{-1} upon complexation indicating coordination of the ligand through oxygen. A new band around 580 cm^{-1} (not present in pure phenol) may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ti-O}}$ ⁶. Sharp bands in the region $385\text{--}390 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ti-Cl}}$ modes.

In the mass spectrum of compound **1**, the molecular ion peak $[M]^+$ has been observed at m/z 416, which corroborates the molecular weight, ir and nmr spectral data. Thus based on limited data available, compound **1** may be considered to assume a monomeric structure.

Reactions of 1 with aliphatic amines : Titanium phenoxides are known to be better acceptors than titanium alkoxides⁷. In view of these ob-

servations, it is therefore proposed to undertake the reactions of **1** with some aliphatic amines, such as diethylamine, n-propylamine, isopropylamine, n-butylamine and t-butylamine. Addition compounds of composition $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2\cdot 2\text{B}$ are formed on mixing **1** with different amines in 1:2 molar ratio in dry benzene. The adducts are quite stable in dry atmosphere. They are non-electrolytes and soluble in common organic solvents. Molecular weight determination (cryoscopy in nitrobenzene) shows them to be monomeric.

Sharp ir bands at 575–580 and 385–410 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ti-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Ti-Cl}}$ modes respectively. The new bands at 280–285 cm^{-1} (not present in parent compound **1**) are assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ti-N}}$ stretching modes⁸. The trends in the shifts of ν_{NH} , ν_{CN} and the (H–N–C) deformation modes are in agreement with the earlier reports on similar addition compounds with alkoxides and phenoxides⁹.

In view of these observations, an octahedral structure may be proposed for these adducts.

Experimental

TiCl_4 (Fluka) was used as such and purity of the 4-t-butylphenol was checked from its m.p. (96°). Solvents and amines were made anhydrous before use.

TiCl_4 (1 mmol) was treated with 4-t-butylphenol (2 mmol) in dry benzene and then refluxed for 60 h until the evolution of HCl gas ceased. The resulting solution was concentrated followed by the addition of petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). The resulting dark red coloured solid washed with petroleum ether and dried under reduced pressure to yield $[\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2]$ (Found : Ti, 11.49; Cl, 17.15. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{Ti}$ calcd. for : Ti, 11.43; Cl, 17.02%).

Complex **1** was mixed separately with different aliphatic amines in 1 : 2 ratio in dry benzene.

The reaction was slightly exothermic and the contents were stirred for 2 h at room temperature, then refluxed for 3 h. Addition compounds of composition $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2\cdot 2\text{B}$ were separated as coloured solids by the addition of petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) to the concentrated solution and were dried under reduced pressure. The compounds were recrystallised from chloroform and dried over P_2O_5 . Analytical data of the compounds are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE ADDITION COMPOUNDS OF DICHLORODI(4-T-BUTYLPHENOXY)TITANIUM(IV) WITH ALIPHATIC AMINES

Compd.*	Analysis%: Found/(Calcd.)			
	Ti	Cl	C	H
$\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2\cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{NH}$	8.49 (8.50)	12.58 (12.60)	59.68	8.52
$\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2\cdot 2\text{Pr}^n\text{NH}_2$	8.92 (8.94)	13.24 (13.26)	55.41	7.81
$\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2\cdot 2\text{Pr}^i\text{NH}_2$	8.94 (8.94)	13.25 (13.26)	—	—
$\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2\cdot 2\text{Bu}^n\text{NH}_2$	8.45 (8.50)	12.60 (12.60)	59.68	8.52
$\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t\text{-4})_2\cdot 2\text{Bu}^t\text{NH}_2$	8.52 (8.50)	12.61 (12.60)	—	—

* Et_2NH = diethylamine; Pr^nNH_2 = n-propylamine; Pr^iNH_2 = isopropylamine; Bu^nNH_2 = n-butylamine; Bu^tNH_2 = t-butylamine.

Titanium content in the parent compound and addition compounds was determined by decomposing the respective compounds with concentrated H_2SO_4 and igniting at 700–800° until a constant weight of TiO_2 was obtained while chlorine was determined by Volhard's method.

Elemental analyses are recorded on a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyser. M.ps. were determined in a Mettler FP-1 apparatus. Conductance of 10^{-3} M solution of the compounds in PhNO_2 was measured on an Elico CM 82 conductivity bridge. Molecular weight was determined in dry benzene using a Beckmann thermometer. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were scanned on a Beckmann spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr spectrum on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer using TMS as an external standard and mass spectrum on a Varian MAT-711 spectrometer.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. (Dr.) Dieter Kummer of Institut für Anorganische Chemie der Universität, Karlsruhe (Germany) for sending the mass spectrum of the compound. The award of a Junior Research Fellowship by U.G.C., New Delhi, to one of the authors (S.S.B.) is also gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. L. R. CHAMBERLAIN, I. P. ROTHWELL and J. C. HUFFMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **104**, 7338; L. R. CHAMBERLAIN, J. KEDDINGTON and I. P. ROTHWELL, *Organometallics*, 1982, **1**, 1098; L. R. CHAMBERLAIN, J. KEDDINGTON, I. P. ROTHWELL and J. C. HUFFMAN, *Organometallics*, 1982, **1**, 1538.
2. L. R. CHAMBERLAIN and I. P. ROTHWELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 1665.
3. K. C. MALHOTRA, N. SHARMA, S. S. BHATT and S. C. CHAUDHRY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 830.
4. S. C. CHAUDHRY and J. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 914.
5. A. SHAH, A. SINGH and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Polyhedron*, 1986, **5**, 1285.
6. R. C. PAUL, P. K. GUPTA, M. GULATI and S. L. CHADHA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **13**, 665; R. C. PAUL, P. SHARMA, P. K. GUPTA and S. L. CHADHA, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1976, **20**, 7.
7. M. J. FRAZER and Z. GOFFER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 2410.
8. D. HORLEY and C. DOJORDJEVIC, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 2322.
9. H. J. BERNSTEIN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, **18**, 161; J. E. STEWART, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1959, **30**, 1259; L. K. DYALL and J. E. KEMP, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1966, **22**, 467; A. J. MORITZ, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1960, **16**, 1176.

